

Anti-Plagiarism System for Exam Monitoring

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Abstract—The rise of academic dishonesty through exam cheating has created more advanced and complex plagiarism detection systems. These systems are proprietary; they come with financial, hardware, privacy, and cloud requirements that can't be covered by all educational institutions. An open-source real-time video plagiarism detection system focused on suspicious gaze direction and cheating device detection, which can run on accessible hardware, is proposed. For the gaze direction detection, the system uses the MediaPipe Face Mesh landmarks, a Kalman filter, horizontal ratio, vertical ratio, and dynamic thresholds to obtain an accuracy of 92.4% with a latency of under 100 ms on our own proposed gaze direction manually annotated dataset. The object detection part is done by two YOLOv8 models fine-tuned with two specific datasets to offer an 88.6% smartphone detection 92.5% smartwatch detection with under 200 ms latency. The system runs only on a CPU with a memory footprint under 820 MB, with over 25 FPS. It only stores the suspicious parts in the entire video, making it suitable to use on small educational institution systems and reducing privacy concerns for storage.

Index Terms—Academic integrity, Educational technology, Gaze tracking, Object detection, Real-time systems, Kalman Filters

I. INTRODUCTION

The educational system is one of the pillars of human society. The changes made are seen years after their implementation. A known "disease" of an educational system is represented by academic dishonesty, and specifically cheating. These habits are shown to decrease the quality, credibility, and image of the entire educational system [1], [2]. Post-2019 Covid pandemic studies [3]–[6] have shown a rise in the number of exam frauds.

To stop this trend, multiple proctoring systems have been implemented in the educational systems [7], which are proprietary and still have flaws unknown to the exterminators. Even so, a gathering of the techniques can be seen: smart cheating devices, suspicious eye movements [8], text analysis for plagiarism using natural language processing [9], body movements, audio, and video recording. These systems are efficient and integrate with the management systems of the educational institutes [10], are leveraging the use of cloud platforms [11], or are using advanced machine learning techniques [12].

The requirements for these solutions are seen as feasible for university-grade educational institutes, but for smaller ones,

they might be unreachable. The latter ones might not have the financial space to use these proprietary solutions, an in-house cloud system, or the necessary hardware requirements, such as a GPU for running the necessary machine learning modes.

In this paper, we offer an open-source video plagiarism detection system. The system can run only on CPU systems and offers real-time processing, without the need for unnecessary recording. It has two main components:

- Suspicious gaze detection - inspired by real-time face detection algorithms [13]–[15] and behavior analysis by using eye tracking [16]–[18]
- Smart cheating devices detection - Two real-time YOLOv8 models for smartphone and smartwatch detections.

The entire system offers the following accuracies 92.4% gaze detection, 88.6% smartphone detection 92.5% smartwatch detection. It has a CPU utilization under 10% of an I5-7300HQ and under 820 MB memory usage. This shows that a real-time system can be implemented on accessible hardware without using GPU resources or external cloud processing [19].

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section II, we present the computer vision techniques used. In Section III, we introduce the system architecture. The implementation details are discussed in Section IV. We show the results of the system in Section V. In Section VI, we share our discussion. Lastly, we conclude our paper in Section VII and discuss the future scope of this work.

II. BACKGROUND

Detecting facial landmarks is critical for detecting suspicious activities. MediaPipe Face Mesh [20] can detect 468 accurate 3D landmarks of the face in real-time. This is better than the 68 landmarks widely used in the past [13], [14]. Such dense landmarks can help the examiner find locations of eyes, irises, and face outlines. This will let the system track the direction of gaze despite variations in illumination and head movements. With facial landmarks, the gaze direction can be inferred and tell if the student is looking to the side or down at cheat sheets more often than usual. Since eye movements can be jittery and the detector can also fail for a few frames, the system needs to smooth the gaze trajectory using Kalman filters [15], [21], [22],

which can help model to improve the smooth eye movements and eliminate sudden transitions in landmark locations.

Object detection is necessary to recognize unauthorized devices (smartphones, smartwatches) in the exam room. YOLO (You Only Look Once) is designed to provide fast and accurate detection of small objects in video frames, allowing real-time processing on standard hardware. YOLOv8 uses optimized convolutional neural network architectures for speed and accuracy. It has significantly fewer parameters and computational costs compared to previous versions. These models can be trained on custom datasets to recognize exam-specific devices and maintain low false alarm rates, even in challenging lighting or background conditions.

Current automated anti-plagiarism systems built on AI are monitoring the suspicious behavior of students taking exams online. Some of the latest [3], [4], [7], [8], [23] make use of convolutional neural networks (CNN) for face and object detection, while the LSTM networks are applied to the detection of temporal activities (for example, the gaze behavior or the repetition of some movements in time). A key feature of the proposed method is that it works entirely offline without relying on cloud services or third party servers. This helps with privacy and cost. The system can also run on regular CPU hardware, which means it could be used by schools or universities with limited computing resources. The system’s combination of gaze detection, object recognition, and temporal analysis gives it the ability to address a wide range of potential cheating behaviors, whereas systems that rely on screen-capture or human supervision alone are often limited in scope.

III. ARCHITECTURE

The anti-plagiarism system uses a modular architecture with five components: facial detection, gaze analysis, object detection, violation monitoring, and report generating. The facial detection module identifies faces and extracts 468-point landmarks. The gaze analysis module uses these landmarks to calculate the candidate’s gaze direction and flag abnormal looking-away behavior. The object detection module uses two YOLOv8 models to detect unauthorized devices (smartphones, smartwatches) in the scene. The violation monitoring module fuses information from the gaze and object detectors to identify exam rule violations. Finally, the report generation module logs the session results and creates a monitoring report.

The gaze analysis subsystem fuses MediaPipe Face Mesh landmark coordinates to infer a candidate’s gaze direction. We use key locations to compute a horizontal and vertical gaze ratio and further apply Kalman filtering for smoothing. The module labels the gaze as left/right, center/down and thus reports if the eyes have deviated abnormally from expected exam behavior.

The object detection framework is based on tailored recognition models to capture unauthorized devices. The infrastructure relies on different detection pipelines for various device types, allowing for fine-tuned recognition thresholds and fewer misclassifications. The approach allows for real-time processing and utilizes smart frame selection strategies

for detection accuracy and computational efficiency. The framework processes the video stream at an optimal interval and reports immediate violations.

The design of the system uses a publisher-subscriber style communication between the individual detection modules and the central violation monitoring module. The asynchronous design allows to meet different processing demands of detection algorithms while keeping the system responsive. The violation monitoring module provides the central coordination and merges the signals from different independent detections. The time-dimension is considered to avoid false positives due to short-lived natural movements and also allow for reactions to actual violations. Asynchronous communication between the modules using PyQt5 signals allows to implement responsive UI with an independent processing threads for each detection module.

Two UML diagrams have been created to provide an example of the system structure and workings: the activity diagram and the sequence diagram. These diagrams show the system from different angles and provide different levels of abstraction. The activity diagram in Fig. 1 shows the places for decision-making, and which execution can be made in parallel.

Fig. 1. Activity diagram of the anti-plagiarism system

The activity diagram shows the working process, starting with the system initialization by Start Monitoring, which is activated by users starting the monitoring by the graphical interface. The Initialize Camera process sets the capture parameters and connects to the webcam with error checking with the Available decision point. The Runtime Camera Health Monitoring is one important feature that was introduced in the

system implementation is the continuous monitoring of camera status within the Capture Frame work flow. The failure to capture frames more than a few times (which is a symptom of camera loss) results in a safe emergency abort sequence to the Skip processing bypass of the remaining actions and terminate to the cleanup work flow. This can result in clean exits in an emergency abort state when the camera is not accessible during an exam session instead of the program just hanging or crashing. The process splits into two streams: Behavioral Analysis Stream and The Object Detection Stream. Behavioral Analysis Stream runs MediaPipe Face Mesh for 468-point facial landmark detection, followed by Check Gaze that uses the horizontal and vertical ratio algorithms for gaze direction analysis. The Object Detection Stream handles Detect Objects using dual YOLOv8 models for mobile smartphones and smartwatches. The Detected decision applies confidence thresholds (0.65 for both), resulting in Object Alert for unauthorized devices. The Robust Error Handling Update Interface updates the screen using PyQt5 signals, showing information such as camera status to the supervisor. The monitoring loop returns to Capture Frame for continuous monitoring, or exits to clean-up routines when an exit condition is detected.

The sequence diagram shows (Fig. 2) that system processes and objects are interacting over time. For example, it shows the source and destination for the messages and when they happen. What it also shows is when a process or object becomes active or inactive. This sequence diagram is used to show the system design in real time using parallel processing for face detection and object detection.

Fig. 2. Sequence diagram of the anti-plagiarism system

We can see that there are three parts in this sequence diagram. They are the initialization, the monitoring loop, and finally, the orderly shutdown. The monitoring loop shows that the system processes frames in parallel: VideoHandler sends frames simultaneously to both Face Detector (for gaze tracking with MediaPipe's 468 facial landmarks) and to Object Detector (for smartphone and smartwatch detection using YOLOv8). Both detection results are then sent to ViolationMonitor for analysis. Finally, it is important that the return flow, from ViolationMonitor to GUI, is done asynchronously. This is with PyQt5's signal and slot method. This allows the GUI to continue

updating without having to wait for the detections to finish. In other words, it does not let the GUI freeze when it is taking a while for the detection algorithms to process the data.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

For making the implementation easily integrate in multiple systems, Python was used together with libraries like OpenCV, MediaPipe Face Mesh, PyQt5 and PyTorch. The system was tested on Linux-based systems like Ubuntu 22.04/24.04 and Windows 11. A requirement for the implementation is to be able to only use CPU resources.

The first stage of the pipeline is the integration of the MediaPipe Face Mesh, which offers multiple landmarks for the face of a person. Important in the implementation and user are: nose tip (x_n, y_n) , forehead (x_f, y_f) , chin (x_c, y_c) , and the face boundaries left (x_l, y_l) and right (x_r, y_r) . These values are used to compute the horizontal ratio H_R and vertical ratio V_R :

$$H_R = \frac{x_n - x_l}{x_r - x_l} \quad (1)$$

$$V_R = \frac{y_n - y_f}{y_c - y_f} \quad (2)$$

For the pupil coordinates, the following Kalman Filter is used. The system uses a constant velocity motion model, with state vector $\mathbf{x}_k = [x, y, v_x, v_y]^T$ encoding the pupil coordinates and velocity components. The initial state vector is set to the first detected pupil coordinates (x_0, y_0) with zero velocity: $\mathbf{x}_0 = [x_0, y_0, 0, 0]^T$. The initial error covariance is set to $\mathbf{P}_0 = \mathbf{I}_4$. The state transition matrix:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Because we have frequent and reliable measurements, we use a simple and stable process noise covariance matrix:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.01 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.01 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The measurement noise is adaptive:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} r & 0 \\ 0 & r \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where $r = 0.1 * c^{-1}$, and c is the confidence. Filter prediction step is computed as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}_{k-1|k-1} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1}\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{Q} \quad (7)$$

The correction step incorporates measurements with adaptive gain:

$$\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}^T(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R})^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{H} is used to extract position measurements and has the value:

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The unit of measurement is pixels for the coordinates and pixels per frame for velocity. A constraint on directed velocity of $v_{max} = 50$ pixels/frame and a constraint on the Euclidean distance of $d_{max} = 30$ for sequential measurements is used to ensure physically realistic tracking [17]. Facial landmark detection from MediaPipe is used for locating the eye regions of interest, which is then used by pupil detection algorithms to deduce the specific location of the pupil in the cropped region. Kalman filtering is used on the pupil coordinates to provide temporal smoothing.

To classify the gaze direction of the face we are using the values of the two ratios H_R and V_R on the next thresholds:

- Left classification $H_R > H_R^L$, where $H_R^L = 0.65$.
- Right classification $H_R < H_R^R$, where $H_R^R = 0.35$.
- Down classification $V_R > V_R^D$, where $V_R^D = 0.6$ and can be combined with the previous classifications.
- Center classification for all the other values.

The values of the thresholds were determined experimentally by testing on various realistic situations, in an effort to closely mirror actual examination settings and conditions. The values of the horizontal thresholds $H_R^L = 0.65$ and $H_R^R = 0.35$ were set to create a 30% neutral zone in the center that takes into account natural head tilts and asymmetries in the face, while effectively detecting purposeful left or right shifts of gaze towards unauthorized devices. The value of the vertical threshold $V_R^D = 0.6$ was set in order to discern between natural vertical eye movements and deliberate downward gazes at phones or smartwatches on a desk. Thresholds values are dynamically changed using head pose compensation. Head pose compensation computes yaw and pitch angles from MediaPipe landmarks based on the nose (x_n, y_n) and face width W_f and height H_f : (yaw) $\theta = 2 \times x_n \times W_f^{-1} \times 30$ and (pitch) $\phi = 2 \times y_n \times H_f^{-1} \times 25$. If $\theta > 15$, then $H_R^{L/R} = H_R^{L/R} + 0.1$. If $\theta < 15$, then $H_R^{L/R} = H_R^{L/R} - 0.1$, and if $\phi > 10$, then $V_R^D = V_R^D - 0.1$.

The next stage in the pipeline is the detection of the objects with the two YOLOv8 models. The complete training implementation is available in the project repository¹.

The smartphone model is based on the YOLOv8n architecture for which we used the phone detection dataset [24] containing 21,099 total images with the following data separation: 19,848 training images (94%), 777 validation images (4%), and 474 test images (2%). The training was configured with the following parameters: 100 epochs with early stopping patience of 20; batch size: 32; image size: 640x640 pixels; optimizer: AdamW with learning rate 0.01; Data augmentation: Mosaic, rectangular training, cosine learning rate scheduling; on GPU using CUDA. The dataset included preprocessing and augmentation techniques such

as horizontal/vertical flips, rotations ($\pm 15^\circ$), shearing ($\pm 10^\circ$), brightness/exposure adjustments ($\pm 15\%/ \pm 10\%$), and various noise additions to improve model robustness.

The smartwatch detection model follows the same YOLOv8n architecture, trained on a watch dataset [25] containing 2,641 total images with the following data separation: 2,259 training images (86%), 255 validation images (10%), and 127 test images (5%). The training configuration included the following parameters: 100 epochs with early stopping patience of 20; batch size: 32 ; image size: 640x640 pixels ; optimizer: AdamW with learning rate 0.01; on GPU using CUDA.

The original dataset contained no augmentations and it was implemented during training to improve model robustness, so we applied:

- **Geometric transformations:** Horizontal/vertical flips (50% probability), rotations ($\pm 15^\circ$), translations ($\pm 10\%$), scaling ($\pm 20\%$), shearing ($\pm 10^\circ$)
- **Color space augmentations:** HSV adjustments (hue $\pm 1.5\%$, saturation $\pm 25\%$, value $\pm 15\%$)
- **Advanced techniques:** Mosaic augmentation, MixUp (10% probability), CopyPaste (10% probability), RandAugment, random erasing (40% probability)
- **Training optimizations:** Rectangular training, cosine learning rate scheduling

The UI interface based on PyQt5 is using an publisher-subscription model to allow asynchronous communication. The publishers have the following different rates which offer a trade-of between accuracy and performance:

- Every 3 frames compute H_R and V_R .
- Every 25 frames update thresholds H_R^L, H_R^R, V_R^D .
- Every 20 frames object detection.

V. EVALUATION

The system has been tested on a laptop with Pop!_OS 22.04 LTS (Ubuntu 22.04 LTS based), Linux kernel 6.12.10, Intel Core i5-7300HQ CPU @ 2.50GHz, 7.6GB of RAM, Python 3.11.13, PyTorch and Ultralytics YOLO framework for object detection. As a video capturing device, a full HD camera (Microdia USB 2.0 Camera, device ID 0c45: 636b) is used instead of the built-in laptop webcam to get a better quality of images for proper detection during the exam. YOLOv8 models are trained on Kaggle.com's cloud services with Tesla T4 GPU, because it trained both models in a reasonable amount of time (5.432 hours for smartphone model and 0.494 hours for smartwatch model).

In order to evaluate the gaze classification system, a dataset was created. The dataset contains 16 participants (14 males, 2 females, with age between 20-30) divided and manual annotated in 25 left gaze direction, 25 right gaze direction, 25 down gaze direction and 25 center gaze directions, contributing to a total of 1600 images.

Table I has the accuracy of the MediaPipe Face Mesh accuracy on our datasets for detecting faces and computed landmarks. Table II contains the accuracy of our gaze classification when the face landmarks are present so it can

¹<https://github.com/Pletea-Marinescu-Valentin/sistem-anti-plagiati>

TABLE I
FACE DETECTION RATES PER GAZE DIRECTION

Gaze Direction	Face Detection Rate (%)	n/N
Center	100.0	400/400
Left	99.5	398/400
Right	96.5	386/400
Down	89.5	358/400
Total	96.4	1542/1600

TABLE II
GAZE DETECTION ACCURACY FOR DETECTED FACES

Gaze Direction	Accuracy (%)	n/N	H_R/V_R
Center	89.5	358/400	0.512 / 0.566
Left	100.0	398/398	0.960 / 0.588
Right	97.9	378/386	0.064 / 0.583
Down	96.4	345/358	0.483 / 0.681
Total	95.9	1479/1542	–
Combined	92.4	1479/1600	–

compute H_R and V_R . The combined accuracy of the two systems is 92.4%.

Performance analysis reveals real-time processing at 25.3 FPS with 45.1ms face detection latency and 44.9ms total system latency. YOLO object detection (198.9ms) runs asynchronously every 20 frames, maintaining system responsiveness while consuming 819.6MB memory and 10% CPU during active monitoring.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF TRAINED DETECTION MODELS ON THE TEST SET

Metric	Smartphone Model	Smartwatch Model
mAP50	0.713	0.631
mAP50-95	0.642	0.438
Precision	0.886	0.935
Recall	0.521	0.309

TABLE IV
CONFUSION MATRIX FOR SMARTPHONE DETECTION

True	Predicted	
	Background	Phone
Background	0	255
Phone	223	1007

TABLE V
CONFUSION MATRIX FOR SMARTWATCH DETECTION

True	Predicted	
	Background	Smartwatch
Background	0	43
Smartwatch	24	256

Table III has the values for the training of the two YOLOv8n models and in Tables IV and V we have the confusion matrices for the two models on the test images.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

Our offline CPU-based design also does not cause data privacy concerns and incurs no extra cost. Although [23] applies

YOLO to detect cheating, their proposed architecture is mainly built on the basis of object detection without combining other sophisticated gaze-tracking or facial behavior modules. Our architecture, on the other hand, is designed by leveraging the YOLO object detection, MediaPipe Face Mesh [20] and Kalman filtering [21], [22] to obtain more information about the cheating, combining device detection with gaze-related suspicious behavior detection.

The survey [3], indicates that the AI-based anti-plagiarism systems usually rely on cloud-based applications or high-performance graphics cards, which in turn raise more privacy issues and cost constraints. Our work overcomes these issues by working in a fully offline CPU mode. It does not require a constant network connection for remote data processing and storage and can keep the students' data on-premise.

On the other hand, [4] applies LSTM to study students' behavior from their temporal activity patterns, while we design a system architecture that works in real time and can also obtain high accuracy in gaze and object detection. To be specific, the gaze prediction accuracy reaches 92.4% in the whole process, and the smartphone detection accuracy reaches 88.6%, while smartwatch detection achieves 93.5% due to the test dataset. The lower accuracy of the downward gaze (89.5%) is because, in the downward gaze state, a part of the pupils is covered by eyelids and therefore there is a higher possibility of the wrong prediction of MediaPipe landmark detection.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The paper introduces a system for anti-cheating surveillance that aims to overcome the shortcomings of existing examination monitoring systems using computer vision and machine learning algorithms. The modular design effectively integrates MediaPipe Face Mesh 468-point facial landmark model with a pair of YOLOv8 object detectors, resulting in an overall gaze accuracy of 92.4% and smartphone detection rate of 84% while maintaining real-time performance on standard hardware.

Contributions of the paper:

- Behavioral analytics with MediaPipe Face Mesh (468 landmarks, higher accuracy than 68-point models)
- Gaze tracking using Kalman filter to detect suspicious movements
- Specialized object detection for exam settings
- Cross-platform deployment without GPU requirement

Performance metrics highlight significant advantages over commercial alternatives, including full privacy control by avoiding cloud-based services, and extended operational duration of over 3 hours with a maximum CPU utilization of 27% on Intel i5 CPUs. Rigorous experimental validation on a diverse set of 1,600 test images from 16 individuals confirms the system's effectiveness across all gaze directions, with particularly strong performance in challenging downward gaze detection scenarios (96.4% accuracy for detected faces).

Future work involves expanding object detection to include more types of unauthorized devices, implementing advanced behavioral pattern recognition for detecting collaborative

cheating, and integrating natural language processing for audio detection.

In summary, the implementation effectively bridges the gap between advanced computer vision research and practical educational applications, providing institutions with accessible and efficient monitoring capabilities to maintain academic integrity standards.

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